

A case of 47, XYY in association with congenital anomalies in teenage couple

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Objective

We present a case of prenatal detected anomalies such as fetal vermian hypoplasia, enlarged cisterna magna, dilated fetal bowel, fixed talipes, detected by ultrasound, presents with karyotype 47, XYY in teenage couple.

Methods

Case report.

Results

The male fetus, of a 16 year-old gravida 1para, her spouse was 16 year-old. Fetal ultrasonography revealed a fetal vermian hypoplasia, enlarged cisterna magna, dilated fetal bowel, fixed talipes, detected at a 29 weeks of gestation. A termination of pregnancy was performed.

Conclusion

Birth anomalies are not found in relation to karyotype 47, XYY, and fetuses with 47, XYY typically do not have an abnormal ultrasound. Thus cases of 47, XYY syndrome will most likely be diagnosed prenatally incidental to a cytogenetic analysis for other reasons. It is known that teenage pregnancy increases the risks of congenital anomalies in central nervous, gastrointestinal and musculoskeletal systems. Karyotype 47, XYY is always of paternal origin and results either from nondisjunction in the second meiotic division during spermatogenesis or post zygotic mitosis. However, relatively little is known about the association between paternally derived aneuploidy and paternally teenage age.